

Tendencies of International Migration of Workforce in Georgia

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Abstract

International migration of workforce is inseparable part of world business life. Work potential, being a significant factor in manufacture both in state as well as internationally, looks for place and means where it's more effective use will be possible.

Workforce migration is one of the most complicated aspects of social life exposing various sides of social-political and economic development of countries and regions. The actuality of migration movements is as well conditioned by its close relation to various sides of social life affecting it significantly and from different perspectives. At the same time, due to social interests, migration processes do not always develop in an optimal way. The purpose of article is studying trends of the international migration of labor from 90s until today. Therefore, to get thorough understanding of its nature it is necessary to get aware of the mechanisms causing migration, its directions, intensity, etc.

Key Words: workforce, international migration, labor market, demographical development, employment of population.

J.E.L. classification: A1

1. Introduction

Georgia's current socio-economic reforms, processes regarding establishment of market interactions started in the 90-ies of the previous century and conditioned basic structural changes in country's economy being accompanied by the decline in production levels, increase in redundancy of workers resulting in serious employment problems. Being unable to realize their educational, intellectual and professional potential certain number of the country's population had to emigrate abroad. Tense social conditions as well have dramatically increased intensity of internal as well as external migration. Consequently, the number of emigrated population has risen with high percentage of highly professional and qualified people. This process continues till now.

The current tendencies of external migration have made significant influence on the change of workforce supply to the labor market of the country, rates and dynamics of unemployment and employment. The dramatic decline in qualified human resources supply have essentially influenced economic activity level of the population and employment rates.

The purpose of article is studying of features of migration and migration processes in Georgia from 90th years of the last century.

For achievement of this purpose set the following tasks: Study the causes of migration, the direction and intensity. Study migration flows, statistical data on money transfers and need of the solution of these problems that is an opportunity for stable development of the country.

2. Literature review

The presented work is based on official statistical sources, scientific research and articles. Papers of researchers were studied during the work: 1. Chelidze N., Tukhashvili M., 2003. Labor Emigration Factors for Georgian Population and Social-Economic results. Migration Processes in Post-Soviet Georgia.. Tbilisi: Tbilisi State University; 2. Toria M., 2008. International Migration Regulation of Workforce in circumstances of Economic Globalization. *Economy and Business*, # 6; 3. Toria M., 2007. International Labor Market and its Influence on Workforce Migration. *Social Economics*, # 3, essence of labor migration, which means process of relocation from one country to another country because of employment and also the happening changes in the Georgian labor market since the last century, from 90th years so far and features of labor migration.

Results of migration processes of this period, reduction of the population and increase in number of migrants of the Georgian population had a destructive impact on national economy in different countries. For the analysis we will consider the material developed in articles: N. Zazadze, 2014. Formation of International Labor Market in Globalized World. International Scientific Conference "Globalization and Statistics". Tbilisi State University, Conference Proceedings. p. 184

Researches also show, that inflow of currency by migrants contributes to normalization of a financial situation, what is also important for economy of the donor countries. By consideration positive aspects of the money transfers made by migrants we processed official statistical data (http://migration.commission.ge/files/census_release_geo_2016.pdf.) of National bank of Georgia. (<https://www.nbg.gov.ge/index.php?m=306>).

Our research was concentrated on labor migration and was studied census reports of 2014 of National statistical office of Georgia in which the total number of emigrants and a percentage share of immigrants among women and men according to gender and age indicators was revealed. We also studied the number of migrants over the different countries. The present situation with the international migration of labor demands deeper studying, the analysis of the existing trends based on migration policy of the country. As for migration policy, we discussed work "A migration profile of Georgia in 2017" in which it is emphasized that migration processes are one of country priorities. (http://migration.commission.ge/files/migraciis_profil_2017_a4_new_1.pdf).

3. Research methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of work is made by works of domestic scientists-economists, official documents of the Government of Georgia, scientific articles and statistical materials. At works on article methods of a theoretical-empirical research, the statistical and economic analysis and synthesis, the historical and logical argument were applied.

The empirical base was made by periodicals materials, data of statistical reports and reference books and also materials of sociological inspection

4. Findings

In recent years, the intensity of migration flows has significantly increased causing some problems both in labor importing and exporting countries. It should also be noted that the socio-economic and demographic consequences of international migration of human resources, professional and qualification composition, directions and magnitude of migrants vary from country to country greatly depending on their socio-economic conditions.

The number of population in Georgia during 1990-2018 decreased by 1 million 694.8 thousand i.e. 31.2%. Population decrease rates were especially high in 1992-2002 when the number of people in the country decreased by more than a million people. Namely, based on the materials of the Migration Control Department of the Ministry of Internally Displaced persons from the occupied regions, by the data of January 1, 2001 Georgia lost 995 thousand people as a result of external migration. 670 thousand out of them went to Russia, 40000 to Ukraine and 50000 to other Post-Soviet countries; 235 thousand people went to other countries, among them 100 migrated to Greece, 30 to Germany, 30 to the Netherlands, 20

to Turkey and 15 000 went to the United States. According to other data, Georgia has approximately 1.5 million migrants and the majority of them 2/3 being labor migrants." (Zazadze, 2014, p.184).

The current situation in migration processes has had a significant impact on those developments conditioned by general economic, political and social crisis developed in the country that had a devastating impact on the socio-economic development of the country.

Thus, we can conclude that in the 90s of the last century, basic changes, radical economic and political reforms accompanied by economic crisis, sharp decline in employment levels led to the intensified migration of the population and this process still continues.

The results of international migration of human resources for Georgia, as for the country exporting predominantly human resources, are miscellaneous. Specifically, on the one hand, the country experiences significant outflow of young people having a great impact on the country's gender-age structure of the population, accelerates the demographic aging process of the population. On the other hand, the share of skilful and highly educated staff who left the country is high which also negatively affects the quality parameters of the workforce in the labor market.

Nevertheless, the migration of human resources has miscellaneous impact on the exporting country. In particular, it has some positive results at the same time. In this regard, direct cash transfers made by migrant citizens have been of great importance for Georgia being the only source of income for thousands of families in the country for years. According to the data provided by the National Bank of Georgia, in 2018 1.57 billion dollar entered through transfer in Georgia 28.9% being from Russia. Regarding the amount of money transfer from the EU member states the leading four countries are Italy, Greece, Spain and Germany. On the whole, the leading countries are Russia (457 million dollars), Italy 191 million dollars), Greece (170 million dollars), the US (159 million dollars), Israel (151 million dollars). <https://www.nbg.gov.ge/index.php?m=306>.

In this regard we would like to note that most of the emigrated workforce from Georgia, particularly in the 90s of the last century, immigrated to Russia. This was influenced by many factors among which economic factor was not the last one. However, they lie in the depths of cultural, political and geographical factors and only complete and proper awareness of their interaction make it possible to estimate complexity of circumstances that have influenced the directions of international migration from Georgia whether it be cultural relationships formed through decades, non-existence of language barrier or geographical proximity, etc. As a result, we have the situation of significant part of emigrated Georgian workforce being in Russia. However, due to the worsening of political relations with Russia, the number of emigrants from Georgia in Russia has been gradually decreasing in recent years. Naturally, the trends of migration flows departed from Georgia have been affected by fostering the cultural and socio-economic ties with such centers of migration in the world like the US and Western Europe.

Thus, we can conclude that the main source of money transfers received from abroad is the amount of money sent by the immigrant population from Georgia. Consequently, it is perfectly clear why Russia holds the leading position among those top ten countries from where money transfers are made.

It should be noted that money transfers are not the only benefits for those countries exporting human resources. Namely, emigration of human resources reduces tensions in the labor market and unemployment rates. On the other hand, emigrants receive their experience abroad, upgrade their qualification and after returning to their homeland enhance economic activities of the country.

In recent years there has been not only a high level of human resources emigration in Georgia but, at the same time, the number of foreign migrants has been increased. For example, during 2002-2017 the number of migrants in Georgia increased 1.75 times but, however, external over-all migrant balance still remains negative in the country. Moreover, it is noteworthy that the share of the immigrants being able to work is 85% and the same share for emigrants is 87%. It is of special interest that the age group of 20-34 has the highest share among the emigrants.

The number of emigrants in the 2014 census of Georgia's population was 88.5 thousand, including 45.4 % males and 54.6 % - female. The main part of emigrants is in 20-54 age interval (75.1 % of emigrants). In the age group of 39 man emigrants are more than women emigrants, while in the emigrant group of 40 and older we have the opposite picture and the number of women exceeds the number of men. Emigrant women aged 50 and older are twice more than the same age group of men emigrants. The

census shows the majority of emigrants live in the Russian Federation (21.7 %), then comes Greece (15.9 %), Turkey (11.2 %). The majority of emigrants in France, Ukraine and Azerbaijan are men whilst in Greece, Turkey, Italy, Germany, the United States and Spain women prevail." (http://migration.commission.ge/files/census_release_geo_2016.pdf.)

Thus, the extent, directions, socio-economic and demographic implications of external migration in Georgia require a thorough and well thought-out study of these processes, analyzing existing trends and the factors affecting them on which the development and realization of optimal migration policies in the country should be based.

This is precisely what conditioned the necessity of migration strategy development for 2013-2015, where it is stated that migration is a global phenomenon and modern challenge affecting the country's socio-economic development, security and stability. According to the above-mentioned and geopolitical location of Georgia, management of migration processes is one of the priorities of the country.

Obviously, integration into the world economic processes and the international labor distribution means mobility of workforce and this process is objective. Georgia can't be isolated from these processes. It is only about the necessity of regulating migration processes and the need to increase its efficiency.

5. Conclusions

Political and socio-economic reforms which started in the 90s have caused major changes in every direction of social life in the country including spheres of human resources, employment and social care where processes have developed especially in a severe way. Economic crisis, decline in production and limited opportunities for employment have forced a significant part of our country's population to go abroad to realize their professional-qualified potential. Therefore, migration has become far more intensive and this process continues to date.

The rise of external migratory flows of the population contributed to the increase in the amount of money transfers from abroad that has become the source of income for thousands of households.

The age group of young people in external migration is particularly high which creates additional problems in terms of demographic aging and natural growth of the country.

In recent years the migration flows from Georgia have been changing which has had a significant impact on strengthening the cultural and socio-economic ties of our country with such centers of migration in the world like the US and Western Europe.

6. References

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